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D6.2 Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Abstract

This deliverable outlines EVERSE’s project data management plan following EC requirements and recommendations

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
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0.2	22.06.2024	Review and additions to sections	Nikos Pechlivanis, Elena Bakoglidou (CERTH)
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0.7	02.08.2024	Consolidation of feedback	Aspasia Orfanou (CERTH)
0.8	05.08.2024	Review by HZDR	Guido Juckeland (HZDR)
1.0	17.08.2024	Incorporation of feedback and final version by CERTH	Aspasia Orfanou, Fotis Psomopoulos (CERTH)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a required deliverable mandated by the European Commission (EC), designed to fit the project's specific activities. It details the relevant project repositories and their management. Furthermore, the DMP complies with the Grant Agreement Preparation (Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement). This deliverable also includes exemplars of the forms used to collect personal data (contact details) throughout the project.

As a dynamic document, it will undergo regular reviews and updates to ensure it remains pertinent and precise. When major modifications are made in the Grant Agreement and at the conclusion of every reporting period, it shall be specifically reviewed.

1 Assistance in achieving project objectives

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
<p>Objective #1: Build a collaborative, community-led structure for evaluating, verifying, and improving the quality of research software and code, by actively involving researchers, software developers, and other stakeholders in the research community.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective #2: Leverage existing tools and resources to support the evaluation, verification and improvement of research software and code quality, based on existing practices and standards across research communities represented by the five EOSC Science Clusters.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective #3: Establish a sustainable and collaborative ecosystem of stakeholders across the research communities associated with the five EOSC Science Clusters to ensure research software and code quality assurance and support the advancement of reliable and reproducible research.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective #4: Provide a framework that will ensure appropriate recognition, reward, and career development for researchers and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) who implement research software and code quality assurance practices and policies.</p>	<p>Yes</p>

Table 1. Objectives and Contributions

2 Introduction

As the purpose of EVERSE project is to build a European network of Research Software Quality and set the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence, no research data will be processed throughout the duration of the project.

In this Project Data Management Plan, we outline the project data repository and cover the project Ethics Requirements that were not previously discussed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

- ▶ EVERSE Project Repository (3.1) containing:
 - ▶ Summary of EVERSE data repository
 - ▶ Degree of accessibility
 - ▶ Protocols for consent and registration.

- ▶ EVERSE Ethics requirements (3.2) not covered in the Grant Agreement document, including:
 - ▶ Data Protection Officer
 - ▶ Personal Data Collection
 - ▶ Personal Data Transfers
 - ▶ Informed consent procedures
 - ▶ Further of previously collected personal data.
 - ▶ Evaluation of the ethic risks

The deliverable has been drafted by the EVERSE Project Management & Coordination Unit and reviewed by the EVERSE Consortium and the EVERSE Management Board.

3 Summarization of work achieved

3.1 EVERSE Project Repository

3.1.1 Introduction and background

EVERSE uses the [ownCloud](#) facility provided by CERTH, as the host, for data portability and sharing for collaborations, with network protection from next-generation firewalls and physical access control. Within the CERTH ownCloud infrastructure, a repository is created for data storage. Access to the repository is granted, only once the participants have been registered and verified, see [section 5.1 Project participants registration form](#).

Software developed within the EVERSE project will be stored and managed through a [GitHub organization](#).

To further enhance communication within the EVERSE project framework, we will be utilizing several tools:

- [Mattermost](#), provided and hosted by HZDR, will be deployed for internal chat communications, enabling team members to collaborate efficiently in real-time.
- [SYMPA](#), provided and hosted by CERTH, will be used to manage our mailing lists, ensuring seamless and organized email communication across the project.
- [Indico](#) provided and hosted by CERN, will serve as our platform for organizing and managing internal meetings and events, streamlining scheduling and participation.
- Finally, a dedicated [Zenodo community](#) will be established as the official repository for EVERSE documents, allowing us to store and share reports, research, and other work in a citable format, thereby ensuring long-term accessibility and recognition of our contributions.

3.1.2 Project Repository Structure

Top Level Folders	Content
1. Official Project Documentation	Proposal document, Contact Mailing List, Legal documents pertaining to the project: Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement etc
2. WPs	Working folders for the WPs, including working templates drafts for each of the WPs' deliverables and milestones
3. Deliverables & Milestones	Repository for project deliverables and milestones (those under review and submitted documents)
4. Reporting	Reports from all project partners
5. Meetings	Details of all project meetings and events (agendas, rolling minutes, slide presentations etc)
6. Communication	Project branding & style guidelines, press releases, presentations, newsletters etc

7. Other Documents	General files
8. Outreach	Details of all events, workshops, conference proceedings from projects related to our project.

Table 2. Repository structure of the EVERSE project (CERTH's ownCloud)

3.1.3 Accessibility

The EVERSE Project Management & Coordination Unit is in charge of managing the project repository, which is maintained by CERTH's ownCloud infrastructure and accessible to all registered and consenting participants.

3.1.4 Registration

The registration form for new members to the consortium resources (mailing list, storage area etc) is available in [section 5.1](#).

3.2 EVERSE Ethics Requirements

In the following sections we address the Ethics requirements listed in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement:

“Activities raising ethical issues must comply with the additional requirements formulated by the ethics panels (including after checks, reviews or audits; see Article 25).

Before starting an action task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities”.

3.2.1 Data protection

Here we address the Data Protection requirements listed in Article 15 of the Grant Agreement:

“Data processing by the granting authority

Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement.

For grants where the granting authority is the European Commission, an EU regulatory or executive agency, joint undertaking or other EU body, the processing will be subject to Regulation 2018/172515.

Data processing by the beneficiaries

The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/67916).

They must ensure that personal data is:

- *processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects*
- *collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes*
- *adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed*
- *accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date*
- *kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and*
- *processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.*

The beneficiaries may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement. The beneficiaries must ensure that the personnel are under a confidentiality obligation.

The beneficiaries must inform the persons whose data are transferred to the granting authority and provide them with the Portal Privacy Statement”.

3.2.2 Personal Data Collection Management and oversight process

The project will be collecting personal data (contact data) in the following scenarios

- When registering as a project participant, which is required to gain access to the project repository.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institutional email address and telephone number, institute affiliation, country (of employer institution), project role.
- When signing up to attend in-person or virtual meetings, such as project meetings, training events, or workshops.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institutional email address, institute affiliation, gender, dietary requirements, accessibility requirements.

The necessary information for conducting the events will be gathered and stored. The collected data is maintained on CERTH ownCloud repositories for the duration mandated by the EC to ensure registry access for potential audits.

3.2.3 Personal Data Collected

Details of data being collected in the different scenarios (e.g. participants registration, Kick-off meeting registration) can be found in [section 5](#).

In accordance with the Grant Agreement (Annex 1, Part B) “When personal data are collected by project partners, the respective data controllers will adhere to GDPR at all times, following their institutional processes and practices. They will only be stored for the duration needed and will not be used for purposes beyond the effective operation of the EVERSE project”.

3.2.4 Personal Data Transferred from EU to a non-EU country or international organisation

Referring to the Grant Agreement “Some administrative information for the purpose of Project Management (specifically related to planning and hosting events) including names, email address, sex & dietary requirements from attendees from EU countries could be exported when the events will be hosted in non-EU countries. No personal data will be collected and exported for research purposes.”

3.2.5 Personal Data Transferred from non-EU country to the EU

As indicated in the Grant Agreement “*The project will only collect as minimum as necessary personal data for project management purposes (names, contact details on registration forms for events). EVERSE contains beneficiaries from the UK, and during the planned international outreach activities, some personal data from collaborators in Africa could be collected for project management purposes. No personal data will be collected or generated for research purposes.*”

3.2.6 Informed consent procedures

[Section 5](#) contains the personal data (contact details) and the forms used to collect consent for EVERSE to host and handle this information. Sensitive categories of information, are managed for the organization and coordination of project-related events, with the consent of the participants.

3.2.7 Additional handling of previously gathered personal information

EVERSE does not involve further processing of previously collected personal data. All personal data has been gathered through the participant registration form ([section 5.1](#)).

3.2.8 Assessment of the ethical risks associated with the data processing tasks of the project

The gathered personal information (contact details), which has been consented to ([see section 5.1](#)), is essential for the management, monitoring, and supervision of the project. As of the creation of this deliverable, no further risk assessments were deemed necessary.

4 Future Actions

At the time of submission, this deliverable covered the description of the project repository and its management, including the ethics requirements outlined in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement. The document will be continuously updated throughout the lifecycle of the project, and a revised version will be submitted in month 36 (D6.6 “Project Data Management Plan and Updates II”). Moreover, it will be reviewed in the event of changes to the Grant Agreement.

In terms of overall impact of this deliverable, it establishes the foundation for gathering and managing the personal data (contact details) essential for the execution of the project.

5 Annexes

5.1 EVERSE project participants registration form

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

Registration of participation in EVERSE

Fields marked with * are mandatory. ✕

Disclaimer ✕

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

* First Name

* Surname

* Institution/ Organisation (e.g University/Department)

Position (Optional)

* Type of role in the project

Which option best describes your role in the project?

- Scientific/technical (contribute to a WP)
- Administration
- Finance
- Legal

* Country

* Please provide us with your institutional contact details (email). Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question.

If you use a different email for the EC Portal, please provide this here.

* Are you the PI for this project at your Organisation/Institution?

- Yes
- No

If you are not the PI for this proposal, please provide us with the institutional contact details (emails) of your PI. Before doing so, please ensure that you have the PI's permission to share their institutional contact details. Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question.

Please provide us with the institutional contact details (emails) of the admin team member(s) at your institution who will support you in this proposal. Before doing so, please ensure that you have the the relevant admin team members' permission to share their institutional contact details. Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question.

Please provide us with the institutional contact details (emails) of the finance team member(s) at your institution who will support you in this proposal. Before doing so, please ensure that you have the the relevant finance team members' permission to share their institutional contact details. Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question.

Please provide us with the institutional contact details (emails) of the legal team member(s) at your institution who will support you in this proposal. Before doing so, please ensure that you have the the relevant legal team members' permission to share their institutional contact details. Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question.

* Institution/ Organisation address

Note: This information (including city, country and postcode details) will only be used if we need to send you original documents, e.g. certificate of attendance. If not provided now we will need to request it at a later stage.

* Institution/ Organisation Telephone Number

(for urgent communication - e.g. meeting/travel updates)

Social Media Links (e.g LinkedIn, Twitter)

* Which mailing lists would you like to subscribe to?

- WP1: Framework of the European Network of Research Software Quality
- WP2: Community-led best practices for developing high-quality research software
- WP3: Tools and services for software quality and FAIRness
- WP4: EOSC Science Cluster Pilots and Driver projects
- WP5: Capacity building and recognition
- WP6: Project Management & Coordination
- Administration
- Finance
- Legal

*

The data you entered will be used for the dissemination of information pertaining to the execution of the Horizon Europe EVERSE project (Grant number: 101129744)

Submit

5.2 EVERSE Kick-off registration form

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

EVERSE:Participation in Kick off Meeting

Fields marked with * are mandatory. ✕

Disclaimer ✕

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* Name

* Surname

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to answer

* Title of the Organisation

* Email

* Please indicate which WP or Board you represent

- WP1: Framework of the European Network of Research Software Quality
- WP2:Community-led best practices for developing high-quality research software
- WP3:Tools and services for software quality and FAIRness
- WP4: EOSC Science Cluster Pilots and Driver projects
- WP5:Capacity building and recognition
- WP6:Project Management & Coordination
- Management Board
- Legal
- Admin
- Finance

* Type of Participation

- In person
 Online

Participation in an informal chat on 11/03/2024 Morning

- Yes
 No

* Participation in the EVERSE meeting on 11/03/2024

- Yes
 No

* Participation in the EVERSE meeting on 12/03/2024

- Yes
 No

* Participation in the social EVERSE dinner on 12/03/2024

- Yes
 No

* Participation in the joint event on 13/03/2024

- Yes
 No

* Participation in the social joint dinner on 13/03/2024

- Yes
 No

Participation in the OSCARS meeting on 15/03/2024

- Yes
 No

Please inform us for any disability

Do you have any dietary requirements?

- I have no dietary requirements
 Vegan
 Vegetarian
 Other

If other, please specify

* During the meeting, photos and videos will be taken. The material produced will be used only for the needs of the EVERSE project.

- I consent
 I don't consent

Submit